

COGNITIVE POETICS

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Annotation: This article purports to be a short introduction to Cognitive Poetics. After a short introductory section, it will present some aspects of Cognitive Poetics, focussed on a few brief case studies.

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INTRODUCTION

During the past fifty years or so, the word *cognition* has changed its meaning. Originally, it distinguished the rational from the emotional and impulsive aspect of mental life. Now it is used to refer to all information-processing activities of the brain, ranging from the analysis of immediate stimuli to the organisation of subjective experience. In contemporary terminology, cognition includes such processes and phenomena as perception, memory, attention, problem-solving, language, thinking, and imagery. In the phrase *Cognitive Poetics*, the term is used in the latter sense.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cognitive Poetics comes in precisely here: it offers cognitive hypotheses to relate *in a systematic way* “the specific effects of poetry” to “the particular regularities that occur in literary texts”. I shall illustrate this in a moment, with relation to a Hebrew and an English text. But first let us proceed by mentioning a few central assumptions of Cognitive Poetics.

One major assumption of cognitive poetics is that poetry exploits, for aesthetic purposes, cognitive (including linguistic) processes that were initially evolved for non-aesthetic purposes, just as in evolving linguistic ability, old cognitive and

physiological mechanisms were turned to new ends. Such an assumption is more parsimonious than postulating independent aesthetic and/or linguistic mechanisms. The reading of poetry involves the modification (or, sometimes, the deformation) of cognitive processes, and their adaptation for purposes for which they were not originally “devised”. In certain extreme but central cases, this modification may become “organised violence against cognitive processes”, to paraphrase the famous slogan of Russian Formalism. Quite a few (but by no means all) central poetic effects are the result of some drastic interference with, or at least delay of, the regular course of cognitive processes, and the exploitation of its effects for aesthetic purposes. In this respect, one should point out that emotions are efficient orientation devices; and that much manneristic poetry is, precisely, poetry of **disorientation**. The cognitive correlates of poetic processes must be described, then, in three respects: the normal cognitive processes; some kind of modification or disturbance of these processes; and their reorganisation according to different principles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cognitive Poetics may be interested in two complementary issues regarding the creativity and novelty manifested in poetic language. 1: Given that this creative use of language results in the intricacies and complexities of poetic language, what are the *unique* cognitive processes which this complex use of language requires. 2. Given the fact that despite its complexity, poetic language is, in principle, interpretable, what are the general (i.e., non-specific to the poetic use of language) cognitive constraints, the adherence to which, guarantees the interpretability of poetic language.

In the first paragraph of this paper I claimed that language is a highly differentiated logical tool by its very nature, and that it requires special manipulations to convey or evoke with its help

low-differentiated, diffuse emotional qualities. Cognitive Poetics investigates a variety of ways in which poets overcome this problem. One efficient means for this

investigation is to apply to poetry knowledge gained by psychologists concerning the nature of emotions (cf. Tsur, 1978).

Psychologists have discerned the following elements in emotions:

1. Cognitive situation appraisal (“cognitive”, in the first sense);
2. Deviation from normal energy level: increase (gladness, anger), or decrease of energy (sadness, depression, calm);
3. Diffuse information in a highly activated state that is less differentiated than conceptual information;
4. Such information is active in “the back of one’s mind”, without pre-empting everything else.

This comparison of the two passages does not greatly differ from the usual techniques of close reading. Nonetheless, our discussion of consciousness and of the categorization of information conveys several significant contributions. Theories of metaphor explore, typically, such issues as how to furnish the best possible paraphrase for a metaphor, or how people understand novel metaphors. Here we have two metaphors that do not differ significantly in their meanings, but rather in their perceived effects. The cognitive frame of reference has contributed to an explanation of this difference: It has explained the relationship between certain linguistic structures and the “regression” to a low-category mode of perception; it has also explained, in turn, the relationship of such regression to the affective quality of the text, as well as to our cognitive characterization of poetry. We have also indicated how these relationships can be further pursued, so as to relate the texts to the effects of period and style, such as Classic/Romantic. In the present context, it also suggests how this difference may contribute to a distinction between some permanent mood and an altered state of consciousness. One may, further, claim that it was the cognitive framework that suggested these linguistic tools for description; in a different frame of reference these descriptions would have appeared little more than trivial.

CONCLUSION

Now a final comment on this sonnet and other similar ones. According to the conception propounded here, it does not *arouse* an ecstatic experience in the reader; it displays a regional quality which the reader recognises as ecstatic. We have followed at some length the verbal means which contribute to the perception of such an ecstatic regional quality.

This paper expounded some aspects of Cognitive Poetics. Its main object was to present some ways in which cognitive theories can be used systematically to relate the perceived affects of poetry to poetic structures. It explored some poetic techniques by which nonconceptual experiences can be conveyed, or displayed, by the use of language which is conceptual in nature. By the same token, it briefly considered the influence of personality style on the reader's or the critic's ability to respond to the poetic qualities.

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